

THE ISSUE OF EDUCATION AND EDUCATION IN MUSIC TEACHING METHODOLOGY LESSON

Rakhmatova Gulshan Sunnatullo kizi

Gulistan State University

Teacher of the Department of "Traditional Singing and
Instrumental Performance" at the Faculty of Arts

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Abstract: Music teaching methodology is an important subject in the training of a future music teacher. The name of the subject clearly explains its content. That is, this science studies the issues of education of children through the medium of music. In order to master the methodology of music education, it is necessary to include music in the school program, to clearly understand the educational possibilities of the art of music as an object of education for the personality of the modern student.

To solve the complex and multifaceted tasks of education, methodical science uses many other subjects in the curricula. The historical-theoretical series of subjects helps students to understand the unique features of musical art, the reflection of life events in musical images, and the means of musical expression.

Key words: culture, spirituality, debate, problem, music culture, musical knowledge, understanding, competence, skill, formation, worldview.

Introduction:

Knowledge of the history of music, the ability to determine the main directions of its development, the understanding and skills of compositional creativity, musical heritage serve as a basis for educating students' musical tastes, and expands their worldviews.

Literature analysis and methodology

Music education in school serves to form human spirituality. After all, it is important because it forms the level of musical culture. Culture as an indicator of spirituality is a broad concept and one of the most controversial issues. Due to the correct implementation of music culture, a person develops certain musical knowledge, understanding, skills and abilities, which, in turn, make up the musical and spiritual worldview of a person. A person's musical culture is manifested in a set of qualities, such as ability, knowledge, skills, ability to evaluate musical works, and serves as a factor of spiritual growth. Therefore, it is appropriate to start this type of education from the family first of all. Later, this process is improved in secondary school, secondary special and higher stages of education. Of course, the science of music teaching methods at school serves as a basis for the composition of musical culture.

This course also has historical significance in the field of music work with children. It is clear that only a method that has a solid scientific basis, is used in wide practice, has been tested and, at the same time, is constantly being improved. A music teacher should know the characteristics and capabilities of students of each class. It is known that "methodology" is such a part of pedagogy that, on the basis of didactic principles, with the help of a method, the educational process is carried out appropriately and its general and special tasks are solved. For example, how to achieve the educational effect of music, to arouse the interest of students, to organize listening to music for students of junior and middle grades, and to achieve the

competence of active perception of students. At the same time, the methodology also covers specific issues. In the methodology of music education, it is emphasized that the educational process, like any social activity, requires systematic and scientific management.

As mentioned, the music teaching methodology is included in the system of pedagogical sciences and has an independent position in relation to itself. He studies its laws in order to improve the content and methods of music education. The essence of the music teaching methodology is determined by understanding the important role and importance of the art of music in the education of the young generation. It shows that the development of music education as a methodical science is connected with the improvement of society's culture, musical art, and schools.

Music teaching methodology is interconnected with other subjects. As for the methodology related to musicology, it is worth noting that recently more attention has been paid to the improvement of the analysis of musical works. The theory of musicology has a direct influence on the development of content and methods of music education. In solving its problems, the methodology relies on the science of psychology. For example: it is impossible to understand the development of students' perception of music, their creative and musical abilities without knowing the laws of the child's psyche. Also, the methodology solves the problems of this or that material, its volume, and the effects of using the methods in connection with psychology. In studying the students' singing skills and the structure of their unique vocal apparatus, the methodology relies on research in the field of physiology.

Discussion:

The methodology of teaching music based on pedagogy considers education as a process related to many factors. A person's musical culture is formed not only by the influence of school, but also by the family, mass media, and the system of social relations. At the same time, it is natural that the school plays a crucial role in the formation of the musical interests and abilities of schoolchildren, and in the formation of the foundations of musical culture in them.

Music teaching methodology is based on pedagogy and its determination of methods. The development of methods is related to the problems: their interrelationship with the content of music education, the development of students' creative and musical abilities, musical memory and voice, age and individual characteristics of music perception, the possibilities of various musical activities in the development of students, etc. The task of the methodology also includes the improvement of various forms of the educational process. Including music lessons, music electives, and extracurricular activities.

The result:

The methodology of teaching music based on pedagogy considers education as a process related to many factors. A person's musical culture is formed not only by the influence of school, but also by the family, mass media, and the system of social relations. At the same time, it is natural that the school plays a decisive role in the development of students' musical interests and abilities, and in the formation of the foundations of musical culture in them.

Music teaching methodology is based on pedagogy and its methods. The development of methods is related to the following problems: their correlation with the content of music education, the development of students' creative and musical abilities, the possibilities of various musical activities in the development of musical memory and voice, age and individual characteristics of music perception, etc. The task of the methodology also includes

the improvement of various forms of the educational process. Including music lessons, optional music activities, classroom and extracurricular activities (clubs, parties, etc.)

Summary:

So, in terms of its nature and content, the science of the methodology of teaching music at school has a unique place in the system of training future music teachers. It is natural that the importance of this subject will increase as music education is on the path of renewal.

References:

- 1.Akbarov I. Musiqa lug'ati. Toshkent – 1997.
- 2.Karimova D. Musiqiy pedagogik mahorat asoslari. - T.: Iqtisod moliya, 2008.
3. Sharipova G.. Musiqa va uni o'qitish metodikasi (metodik qo'llanma). Toshkent.
- 4.Rakhmatova, G. (2023). SOCIAL PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS IN THE PERFORMANCE OF THE TRADITIONAL SINGER OF THE XXI CENTURY. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(9), 21-24.

